

CENTER PARTNERSHIPS AND ASSOCIATIONS, YRS 1-4

NESCent has entered into a diverse array of partnerships during its first four years. These include:

From the start, NESCent has had a strong relationship with NCEAS. The Directors are in frequent contact (and the Director of NCEAS has provided invaluable advice to the NESCent Director), we have jointly funded 3 working groups thus far, and have partnered on data sharing initiatives. NCEAS is also a co-sponsor of our SACNAS activities. The Directors of NCEAS, the iPlant collaborative and NIMBioS met during the NESCent community summit to discuss ways to establish, continue and increase collaborative programs.

<http://nimbios.org>

<http://www.nceas.ucsb.edu>

We have continued an active collaboration with the Encyclopedia of Life (EoL) initiative, with collaborations with their informatics, education and outreach groups, and the Biodiversity Synthesis Center (BioSYNC). We will be working with the BioSYNC to co-sponsor a hosted event or reception at the SICB 2009 meeting in Boston to share information with conference attendees about funding opportunities within our organizations.

<http://www.eol.org>

Together with the EoL, NESCent organized discussions at the 2008 AToL meeting to address issues of collaboration between AToL projects and EOL.

<http://atol.sdsc.edu>

NESCent has collaborated extensively with the Evolutionary Genomics Center (EGC) of Duke's Institute for Genome Science and Policy. The EGC Director, Greg Wray, is a member of our operations committee; the Center jointly sponsored our 2007 Darwin Day symposium on Genomes and Evolution and the EGC is currently working with our EOG group to develop a summer workshop for faculty at primarily teaching institutions

<http://www.genome.duke.edu/centers/ceg>

NESCent has also co-organized (with Nico Cellinese) a phyloinformatics workshop held at the 2008 TDWG meeting that is being sponsored by the EoL BioSYNC. In addition, NESCent is organizing and sponsoring an ontologies session at 2008 TDWG meeting (and is an institutional member of that organization).

<http://www.tdwg.org>

Associate Director of Informatics Vision attended the iPlant kickoff meeting in April 2008 and is on the steering committee for an iPlant Grand Challenge Workshop on Assembling the Plant Tree of Life. Our EOG group has had initial conversations with this Collaborative about future collaborations, specifically between the education/outreach groups.

<http://iplantcollaborative.org>

In May of 2008 NESCent co-sponsored a meeting with the Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard University to set forth the planning for a joint VertNet database, including the development of community standards and a long term sustainability plan for the most important museum vertebrate databases (HerpNet, ORNIS, MaNIS and BioGeomancer). This meeting resulted in the establishment of a steering committee and

the garnering of initial funds to begin the integration of these databases.

<http://www.herpnet.org/>

<http://www.specifysoftware.org/Informatics/informaticsornis/>

<http://manisnet.org/>

<http://www.biogeomancer.org/>

NESCent Informatics has partnered with the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) project to obtain funding for a helpdesk and user support. NESCent also co-sponsors the development of GMOD data model extension modules to represent evolutionary data types. Other activities include the organization of the annual project meeting in Toronto and organization and hosting of the first-ever GMOD summer school.

<http://www.gmod.org>

Through the Phenoscope project, NESCent co-sponsored a 1-day workshop on Evolution and Ontologies with the National Center for Biomedical Ontologies (NCBO), and continued working in collaboration with the Open Biomedical Ontologies (OBO) consortium and the Zebrafish Information Network (ZFIN). The Center also hosted a summer internship in phenotype informatics supported by the DeepFin RCN.

<http://www.bioontology.org>

<http://www.obofoundry.org>

<http://zfin.org>

<http://www.deepfin.org>

NESCent's Dryad data sharing initiative has received an NSF DBI award that is funding a collaboration among the UNC School of Information & Library Sciences Metadata Research Center, the North Carolina State University Digital Libraries Initiative, the LTER Network, and TreeBASE. The initiative is in partnership with major evolutionary biology and ecology societies, including the American Society of Naturalists, the Ecological Society of America, the Society for the Study of Evolution, the Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology, the Society for Molecular Biology and Evolution, the Paleontology Society, the Society of Systematic Biologists, and the European Society for Evolutionary Biology, as well as independent journals such as Molecular Ecology, Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution, and Evolutionary Applications.

<http://ils.unc.edu/mrc>

<http://www.lib.ncsu.edu/dli>

<http://www.lternet.edu>

<http://www.treebase.org>

NESCent worked with the Morphbank and Morphobank projects to promote interoperability.

<http://www.morphbank.net>

<http://morphobank.geongrid.org>

NESCent is one of the coordinating institutions on a recent NSF INTEROP award that funds an informatics partnership with the LTER network, NCEAS, the Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center, the USGS National Biological Information Infrastructure and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). We are also a coordinating institution in a pending DataNet proposal that involves a network of over 20 partner organizations working on shared infrastructure for Earth-based environmental observation data.

<http://www-eosdis.ornl.gov>

<http://www.nbio.gov>
<http://www.gbif.org>

The Phyloinformatics Hackathon was in partnership with member projects of the Open Bioinformatics Foundation.

<http://www.open-bio.org/>

With Google's sponsorship, we hosted students in the 2007 and 2008 Google Summer of Code program.

<http://code.google.com/soc/2007/>
<http://code.google.com/soc/2008/>

We collaborate with developers at the San Diego Supercomputer Center (SDSC) to define application programming interfaces (APIs) for the CIPRES portal.

<http://www.sdsc.edu>
http://www.phylo.org/sub_sections/portal

Our Summer Courses in Computational Phyloinformatics was with co-sponsorship from CIPRES (Cyberinfrastructure for Phylogenetic Research).

<http://www.phylo.org>

NESCent co-sponsored the Paleobiology Database summer course and the Bodega Bay applied phylogenetics workshop.

<http://paleodb.org/cgi-bin/bridge.pl?user=Guest&action=displayHomePage>
http://bodegaphylo.wikispot.org/Front_Page
<http://www.nescent.org/news/thisweek.php?id=58>

We are a co-sponsor of the Analytic Paleontology Summer Course

<http://www.palass.org/modules.php?name=palaeo&sec=careers&page=165>

NESCent's Assistant Director of Informatics participated in a hackathon focused on web services for bioinformatics, sponsored by the Database Center for Life Sciences in Japan.

<http://hackathon.dbcls.jp>

The 2007 Comparative Methods in R Hackathon involved a working partnership with the developers from multiple open-source programming packages, detailed at the R-phylo wiki.

<http://r-phylo.org>

NESCent has worked with the Australian-New Zealand Research Network for Vegetation Function to co-sponsor a multi-day working group on wood evolution. In addition, NESCent, along with NCEAS and QUEST, have formed a "Networks International Council"; this group meets by conference call ~2X per year to discuss potential collaborations and issues.

<http://www.vegfunction.net>
<http://quest.bris.ac.uk/>

We have worked with the Society for the Study of Evolution (SSE) on several projects, including the development of DRYAD, co-sponsorship of NESCent's SACNAS activities, and co-sponsorship of the presentation at the NABT annual meeting. An EOG staff member is a member of the SSE Education Committee. Our collaboration with SSE continues to expand. They have committed to regular support of the SACNAS events and

they sponsor a presentation at NABT by SSE members which EOG arranges. In addition to serving on the Education Committee we are involved in the development of the teacher workshop associated with the annual conference, and host the “Evolution, Science and Society” website originally posted on EvoNet.

<http://www.evolutionsociety.org>

The American Institute of Biological Science (AIBS) has been an active partner with NESCent from the start. Currently they are co-sponsors of both the NABT Evolution Symposium and NESCent’s SACNAS activities.

<http://www.aibs.org/core/index.html>

We worked with the Biotechnology Center Institute (BTCI) on their Bioethics Forum “Evolution in the 21st Century” and they have expressed interest in a 2009 summer teacher’s workshop on evolution.

<http://www.btc.org/bioethics/default.html>

NESCent has worked actively with the Ecological Society of America (ESA) in efforts to develop digital data registries and repositories for the evolutionary and ecological sciences. In addition, the ESA is a co-sponsor of our SACNAS activities.

<http://www.esa.org>

We have developed a strong relation with Springer Press. EOG staff members and NESCent Sabbatical Scholars are members of the editorial board of the new Springer journal (Evolution: Education and Outreach). In addition, Springer is providing financial support for NESCent’s SACNAS activities.

<http://www.springer.com/east/home/life+sci?SGWID=5-10027-70-173740503-0&detailsPage=journal%7Cdescription>

Sigma Xi, the Scientific Research Society, hosted our 2008 Darwin Day symposium on the Origin and Early Evolution of Life.

<http://www.sigmaxi.org>

NESCent’s EOG group is collaborating with the North Carolina Association for Biomedical Research (NCABR) on education and outreach projects.

<http://www.ncabr.org/>

We are participating with the North Carolina Museum of Natural Science in their Science Café series. We have expanded our collaborations with NCMNS to include a year-long speaker series and a co-sponsorship of a Darwin-themed stage production (entitled “Re: Design”) as part of the 2009 “Year of Darwin” activities. WUNC-TV (local PBS affiliate) and NC State University’s Theater Department are also collaborating on these “Year of Darwin” projects.

<http://www.naturalsciences.org>

<http://www.unctv.org>

<http://www.ncsu.edu/theatre>

We are participating with the Coalition for the Public Understanding of Science (COPUS) in public education initiatives. We are working with COPUS to populate the 2009 Year of Science site, specifically February – Evolution month.

<http://www.copusproject.org>

We worked with the North Carolina School of Science and Math to offer a summer course in teaching evolutionary biology at the elementary school level to teachers.

<http://www.ncssm.edu>

NESCent is collaborating with BioQUEST to develop and disseminate modules based on work by NESCent scientists. Modules have been presented at BSA and BioQUEST workshops.

<http://www.bioquest.org/>

We have collaborated with Understanding Evolution to write a successful CCLI Phase 1 proposal to assess and improve the Evolution in the News program. We are also collaborating on a CCLI Phase 2 proposal to develop a web 2.0 rich “Undergraduate Lounge.” NESCent’s EOG is also collaborating with Understanding Evolution to produce and distribute monthly Evolution in the News stories and podcasts.

<http://evolution.berkeley.edu/>

We are serving on the advisory board for the NSF funded EvoS program expansion.

<http://evolution.binghamton.edu/evos/>

We are collaborating with Scott Edwards (Harvard) and Rich Kliman (Cedar Crest College) to sponsor, organize and facilitate an NSF-funded program which awards undergraduates (primarily from underrepresented groups) travel awards to attend the annual Evolution (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference. While at the conference the students receive mentoring and professional development and present their research at an undergraduate poster session.

<http://www.oeb.harvard.edu/faculty/edwards/community>

<http://www2.cedarcrest.edu/academic/bio/rkliman>

We are collaborating with the Kenan Fellows Program at NC State University by acting as a Kenan Fellowship project mentor for Bruce Boller, a high school teacher from Bertie County, NC and Kenan Fellow awardee.

<http://www.ncsu.edu/kenanfellows>

NESCent underwrites the local science radio show, Radio In Vivo, and works with the host, Ernie Hood, to provide media coverage of NESCent events.

<http://radioinvivo.net/>

NESCent partners with the American Museum of Natural History to recruit instructors for their on-line courses.

<http://www.amnh.org/learn/>

NESCent provided support to the NC Science Blogging Conference.

<http://scienceblogging.com>

A NESCent informatics staff member leads the BioSQL project, which, among other things, provides interoperable storage of taxonomies and phylogenetic trees.

<http://biosql.org>

A NESCent informatics staff member was sponsored by the Database Center for Life Science (DBCLS) and the Computational Biology Research Center (CBRC) in Japan to participate in the BioHackathon 2008, which resulted in the first draft of common phyloinformatics web-services.

<http://dbcls.rois.ac.jp/en/>
<http://www.cbrc.jp/index.eng.html>
<http://hackathon.dbcls.jp/>

NESCent is initiating a partnership with the Open Croquet project and the Renaissance Computing Institute (RENCI) to explore innovations for rich and instant collaboration through virtual 3D worlds.

<http://www.opencroquet.org/>
<http://www.renci.org/>

NESCent Informatics is a participant in the NSF-funded TraitNet Research Coordination Network, and within the partnership contributes to the development of trait ontologies and generic semantics-enabled trait databases.

<http://www.columbia.edu/cu/traitnet/>